

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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The Relationship between Extracurricular Activities and Academic Performance among High School Students

Donwels Ann P. Lastra,* Art Jamel D. Amallarinto, Bryan Noel Angelo C. Deiparine,
Divine Joy D. Montero, Lilian A. Calugay, Janine P. Rulona
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance among high school students at Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. Utilizing a quantitative descriptive-survey research design, the study employed random sampling to select 173 high school students out of 183 high school students from its population. Data were collected using a structured survey instrument designed to assess both the levels of extracurricular participation and academic achievement. The data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's r correlation coefficient. The results indicate that both extracurricular activities and academic performance are observed at high levels among the students, with a Pearson's r correlation of 0.01, suggesting a positive correlation between these two variables. These findings affirm that increased participation in extracurricular activities is significantly associated with higher academic performance. The study highlights the importance of extracurricular engagement in enhancing students' academic outcomes, suggesting potential benefits for educational policy and student development programs.

Keywords: *extracurricular activities, academic performance, high school students, education*

Introduction

Academic performance is an assessment of educational results used to identify how far students' abilities have progressed after learning and practicing (Tusyanah, 2023). In accordance with Hu and Li (2023), students who are more active in class perform better academically. A study conducted by Mappadang et al. (2022) revealed that students who have a greater academic interest are more likely to optimize their learning for improved outcomes.

Two major categories of factors that influence individual well-being, according to (Tusyanah, 2023). The first are internal factors, which include physical well-being and proper sense function, with a special emphasis on vision, hearing, and mental health. There are other psychological factors that include intellectual abilities, talents, and essential daily skills. External factors, such as family dynamics, educational environment, societal conditions, group affiliations, and social contacts with friends, on the other hand, have a considerable impact on an individual's overall sense of well-being. These interrelated factors have a significant impact on an individual's life experiences and overall quality of life.

Extracurricular activities (EAs) on the other hand, are activities that students can participate in outside of the regular school day that are sanctioned by the school. Sports, fine arts programs, clubs, and religious organizations are a few examples (Morris, 2019). As stated by Collings (2020), the impact of extracurricular activity engagement on a student's overall education is a source of concern for students, parents, and educators. Activities were introduced to allow students to explore and expand their learning through extracurricular involvement, which can impact their academic performance due to the need for effective time management (Gilman, 2004). Students participating in extracurricular activities often struggle with managing their time. For example, sports like basketball and volleyball demand substantial energy and dedication. Despite this, these activities significantly benefit students' mental health and personality development. However, they can consume several hours, leaving students with limited time for homework or exam preparation. Nevertheless, an active mind can teach students how to balance both their studies and extracurricular activities effectively. The benefits of extracurricular activities for education are many. Better behavior, higher grades, and personality development—all of which help students become more successful and socially confident adults—are some of these favorable benefits.

There are several existing academic performance and extracurricular activities studies (Freeman, 2017; Castillo, 2023; Laskos, 2019; Correa-Fernandez et al., 2015; Hanks, 2018; Westernberger, 2017). However, there is a dearth of literature that explores thoroughly about the relationship between academic performance and extracurricular activities. The conduct of this study is urgent and necessary to address the common problems that students experience in the context of secondary education learners of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. Additionally, this study further adds to the existing body of literature.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance among high school students. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of extracurricular activities of high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1. physical development;
 - 1.2. social development;

- 1.3. cognitive development; and
- 1.4. emotional development?
2. What is the level of academic performance of high school students in terms of:
 - 2.1. academic self-efficacy;
 - 2.2. achievement motivation;
 - 2.3. academic engagement; and
 - 2.4. social engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance among high school students?

Literature Review

Academic Performance

Academic performance refers to students' ability to handle their studies and complete tasks assigned by teachers, encompassing their capacity to learn, recall facts, and express knowledge (Lamichhane K. et al., 2023). It is a critical indicator of student success and a predictor of future academic and career achievements.

Academic Self-Efficacy. Academic self-efficacy is students' belief in their ability to successfully complete academic assignments (Mulyadi et al., 2016). Honicke and Broadbent (2016) explain that academic self-efficacy shapes students' judgments about their capacity to achieve educational goals, influencing their motivation and performance.

Achievement Motivation. Alyana (2023) defines achievement motivation as a type of social motivation characterized by the desire to attain a specific level of excellence. It drives students to overcome barriers and engage in challenging tasks regularly (Sahu, 2023), fostering perseverance and resilience in academic pursuits.

Academic Engagement. Academic engagement is vital for student success, as engaged students are more attentive and exhibit higher morale (Yudiani et al., 2023). Jaime et al. (2023) describe it as a positive mental state reflecting active participation and commitment to the learning process.

Social Engagement. Socially engaged students are more motivated, participate in campus events, and enjoy a better overall educational experience, which contributes to their academic success (Mouzakis, 2017). Social engagement fosters a supportive learning environment and enhances students' sense of belonging.

Extracurricular Activities

Extracurricular activities are non-required components of academic programs that play a significant role in secondary education today (Datta & Sabuj, 2018). According to Agyekum (2021), these activities include music, athletics, publications, student administration, visual arts, academic clubs, service organizations, and special interest groups, contributing to holistic student development.

Physical Development. Borukova (2023) describes physical development as a lifelong process that begins at birth and continues through adulthood. Participation in sports and physical activities as part of extracurricular programs promotes physical health and fitness.

Social Development. Mohamed (2020) defines social development as the evolution of human interactions and the complex phenomena arising from these interactions, including social networks, values, and institutions. Extracurricular activities like team sports and clubs foster social skills and community involvement.

Cognitive Development. It involves the growth of mental processes such as recall, critical thinking, and decision-making (Ahmad et al., 2016). Curtis (2018) outlines various cognitive skills, including critical thinking and reflective judgment, that are enhanced through academic clubs and competitions.

Emotional Development. According to Kamboj (2023), involves the growth of emotional capacities and effective emotion regulation. Participation in arts and music programs helps students develop emotional expression and resilience.

This literature review underscores the multifaceted benefits of extracurricular activities, highlighting their positive impact on various dimensions of academic performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative non-experimental design method of research using correlation technique was employed in this study. The researchers used descriptive-survey research to identify the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance among the High School Students of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Incorporated. According to Creswell (2014), Quantitative research uses the relationship between variables to evaluate objective theories. Statistical techniques can be used to measure and analyze the variables. In general, quantitative data is gathered in numerical form and analyzed using statistical analysis.

Participants

This research conducted the study at Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy, Incorporated (MHSSI), a Catholic school administered by the Diocesan Clergy of Mindanao. The study occurred at the Governor Generoso campus, specifically at Purok 3, Poblacion, Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental. The focus is on high school students because they will be the ones participating in the research.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Grade and Section</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>No. Of Sample</i>
Grade 7	33	31
St. Lorenzo Ruiz de Manila		
Grade 8	28	27
St. Damien of Molokai		
Grade 9	35	33
Blessed Pier Giorgio Frassati		
Grade 10	36	33
Blessed Carlo Accutis		
Grade 11	34	32
St. Theresa of Calcutta (GAS)		
Grade 12	12	12
St. Francis of Assisi (GAS)		
Grade 12	5	5
St. Ignatius of Loyola (HUMSS)		
Total	183	173

Instruments

The researchers made use of downloaded questionnaires and modified them. There were two collections of downloaded questionnaires garnered from two different studies. Each questionnaire is set for every individual variable, which are: Extracurricular Activities (IV) and Academic Performance (DV).

The first set of questionnaires would state the Independent Variable, Extracurricular Activities stating the indicators: Physical Development, Social Development, Cognitive Development, and Emotional Development.

The second set of questionnaires would state the Dependent Variable, Academic Performance stating the indicators: Academic Self-Efficacy, Achievement Motivation, Academic Engagement, and Social Engagement.

Procedure

This study employs surveys to gather information on students' extracurricular activities and academic performance. The procedure involves obtaining permission from school authorities, securing consent from respondents and their parents, distributing questionnaires, and subsequently collecting, tallying, and analyzing the gathered data to fulfill research objectives. The data will be analyzed by using the pearson-r correlational coefficient to determine the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are integral to this study's conduct. Key elements include ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality, with participants granted anonymity through the use of numbers or aliases. The informed consent process, aligned with ethical guidelines, prioritizes clarity, respect, and agreement to participate at the respondent's convenience. Additionally, measures are taken to mitigate risks, emphasize mutual benefits, and prevent plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, conflict of interest, and deceit throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Extracurricular Activities*

<i>Extracurricular Activities</i>	<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Physical Development	4.09	High
Social Development	4.29	Very High
Cognitive Development	4.17	High
Emotional Development	4.09	High
Overall Mean	4.16	High

In Table 2 below, the level of extracurricular activities among high school students in Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. has an overall mean of 4.16 with the descriptive equivalent of high. The result show that Social Development has the highest average weighted mean value of 4.29 which is describe as very high. Physical and emotional development, on the other hand, have the lowest average weighted mean value of 4.09 which is also considered high. Given that the total mean of 4.16 is within the 3.40–4.19 range, it can be concluded

that Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. high school students frequently participate in extracurricular activities.

In Table 3 below, the level of academic performance among the high school students of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. has an overall mean of 4.16 with the descriptive equivalent of high. Achievement Motivation has the highest average weighted mean value of 4.35 which describes as very high. Meanwhile, Academic Self Efficacy has the lowest average weighted mean value of 4.05 which describes as high. All the indicators got the mean ranging 3.40-4.19, this means that academic performance is observed by the high school students of Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc.

Table 3. *Academic Performance*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Average weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Academic Self Efficacy	4.05	High
Achievement Motivation	4.35	Very High
Academic Engagement	3.94	High
Social Engagement	4.29	Very High
Overall Mean	4.16	High

In Table 4 below are the results of the test of the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance. The relationship is not significant if the p-value is above 0.05. The Extracurricular Activities and Academic Performance has a significant relationship as it has a p-value of 0.01 which is below than 0.05. This means extracurricular activities is correlated with academic performance, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 4. *Correlation Analysis of the Variables*

		<i>Extracurricular Activities</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>
Extracurricular Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.01
	N	2	2
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.01	
	N	2	2

Conclusions

The analysis of the data collected for this study revealed several key findings. Firstly, high levels of participation in extracurricular activities and high academic performance were observed among high school students at Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. Secondly, there is a significant positive correlation between extracurricular activities and academic performance. This indicates that students who are more engaged in extracurricular activities tend to perform better academically. These findings underscore the importance of encouraging students' participation in extracurricular activities as a means to enhance their academic success. Educators and policymakers should consider integrating and promoting diverse extracurricular programs to support holistic student development and improve educational outcomes.

For the future research, firstly, we recommend expanding the scope of this study because it is only being conducted within the boundaries of the Maryknoll High School of Sigaboy Inc., only. The researchers also recommend the use of the Qualitative Research approach in conducting the study to examine further experiences and perspectives revealing important information about the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance.

Researchers can also consider using mixed-methods research, which combines qualitative and quantitative approaches, to improve the comprehensiveness and scope of their study. Future researchers may continue to conduct further studies on the relationship between extracurricular activities and academic performance, develop their research methodologies, and explore additional components of the topic. By continually increasing knowledge through thorough research, the field can help to develop evidence-based approaches and guidelines that enhance academic outcomes for students participating in extracurricular activities.

Lastly, school administrators, teachers, and parents should encourage students to maintain the balance between academics and extracurricular activities. This study implies that a well-rounded student knows how to balance the weight of focus for academics and extracurricular activities in school and that these two factors should complement each other for student success.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Donwels Ann P. Lastra

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Art Jamel D. Amallarinto

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Bryan Noel Angelo C. Deiparine

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Divine Joy D. Montero

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Lilian A. Calugay, LPT

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines

Janine P. Rulona, MAED

Maryknoll School of Sigaboy, Inc. – Philippines